

Release of Mwangaza and Kalalu, early-maturing and rice yellow mottle virus-resistant varieties in Tanzania

A. Luzi-Kihupi, Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA), Department of Crop Science and Production, P.O. Box 3005, Morogoro, Tanzania; F. Shao-Mwalyego, Uyole Agricultural Research Institute, P.O. Box 400, Mbeya, Tanzania; J.A. Zakayo, Dakawa Agro-Scientific Research Centre, P.O. Box 1892, Morogoro, Tanzania; and M. Mkuya, Agricultural Research Institute, Katrin, Private Bag, Ifakara, Tanzania

Tanzania is the second largest producer of rice in Eastern, Central, and Southern Africa after Madagascar. In 2004, the country produced about 680,000 t of rice from an area of 355,000 ha (FAOSTAT 2008). About 74% of the rice in Tanzania is grown under rainfed lowland conditions by smallholder farmers, whereas upland and irrigated rice comprise about 20% and 6% of the area, respectively. The average yield is very low, 1–1.5 t ha⁻¹, as farmers grow a number of traditional varieties that are tall and prone to lodging. Moreover, these varieties have long maturity and are not suitable for areas with a marginal rainfall pattern. The occurrence of rice blast and rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) also contributes to the yield decline.

Rice breeders in Tanzania have been employing both conventional and nonconventional breeding methods, including introduction, hybridization, and mutation breeding, followed by selection. The International Network for the Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER) has played a big role in introducing new genotypes, which are being evaluated by national programs. Some of these genotypes have been released as new varieties; others are used in the hybridization program. Mutagenesis or induced mutation has been employed in the breeding program to reduce plant height and the maturation period of popular indigenous cultivars while maintaining the parents' good quality traits (Luzi-Kihupi and Zakayo 2001).

Rice genotypes consisting of local, exotic, and improved lines/varieties from the breeding program have been screened at SUA for RYMV resistance since 1998. The lines/varieties that showed resistance were subsequently screened for resistance to RYMV under natural conditions in farmers' fields in the southern highlands and the eastern zone of Tanzania. Several genotypes showed resistance, including mutants that were derived from irradiating the popular local cultivar Supa and introduced varieties from the Africa Rice Center (WARDA) and the International Rice Research Institute. In 2005, with the help of participating farmers in these endemic areas, one mutant, SSD 35, derived from irradiating Supa by 170 gray gamma rays, and one introduced line, H232-44-1-1-

1, were recommended for release by the National Variety Release Committee. These new varieties were named Mwangaza and Kalalu, respectively. The new varieties are early-maturing, photoperiod-insensitive, and resistant to RYMV (Tables 1 and 2). Their yield and grain quality are comparable with those popular Supa although the latter is late, photoperiod-sensitive, and susceptible to RYMV.

Table 1. Varietal reaction to RYMV at various locations, 2003.

Variety/line	Source	RYMV score ^a /location				
		SUA	Dakawa	TAC	Kyela	Ndungu
SSD 1	SUA	1	1	1	3	1
SSD 3	SUA	3	3	1	3	3
SSD 5	SUA	1	1	1	1	1
SSD 7	SUA	1	1	1	1	1
SSD 35	SUA	1	1	1	1	1
Gigante (resistant check)	WARDA	3	3	1	1	1
IR53234-27-1	IRRI	1	3	1	1	1
IR47686-15-5-1	IRRI	1	1	1	3	1
H 234-18-1-1	WARDA	1	3	1	3	1
H 232-44-1-1	WARDA	1	3	1	3	1
IRAT 252	IRAT	1	1	1	3	1
Faro 300	Nigeria	1	1	3	3	1
TGR 78	WARDA	1	1	1	3	1
TXD 88	Tanzania	7	7	5	5	9
TXD 85	Tanzania	7	7	5	5	7
Supa (susceptible check)	Tanzania	7	7	5	5	7

^a1 = highly resistant, 3 = resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible.

Table 2. Morphological characteristics of varieties Mwangaza, Kalalu, and Supa.

Characteristic	Variety		
	Mwangaza	Kalalu	Supa (check)
Former designation	Supa SSD 35	H232-44-1-1	Supa India
Cultivar pedigree	Mutant of Supa	Introduced	Local
Proposed areas of release	Rainfed lowland/upland	Rainfed lowland/irrigated	Rainfed lowland
Leaf blade color	Green	Dark green	Green
Leaf sheath color	Green	Green	Green
Leaf blade pubescence	Glabrous	Glabrous	Glabrous
Flag leaf angle	Horizontal	Erect	Intermediate
Plant height (cm)	118	114	130
Panicle type	Heavy	Intermediate	Intermediate

Panicle exertion	Well-exserted	Well-exserted	Well-exserted
Shattering	Low	Moderate to low	Low
Days to 50% flowering	60	70	83
Photoperiod sensitivity	Insensitive	Insensitive	Sensitive
Grain length (mm)	8.0 (extra long)	7.4 (long)	7.9 (extra long)
Grain width (mm)	2.52	2.05	2.80
Grain shape	Slender	Slender	Medium
Seed coat color (bran)	Brown	Straw	Straw
Awn presence	Awned on some spikelets	Absent	Absent
1,000-grain weight (g)	32.1	30.0	34.6
Translucency	<10% chalkiness	Translucent	Translucent
Resistance to RYMV	Highly resistant	Resistant	Susceptible
Resistance to blast	Resistant	Resistant	Susceptible
Amylose content	Intermediate	Low	Intermediate
Gelatinization temperature	Intermediate	Soft	Intermediate
Gel consistency	Soft	Medium	Soft
Scent (aroma)	Nonscented	Nonscented	Scented
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	2–3	2–3	2–3

References

FAOSTAT. 2008. <http://faostat.fao.org>.

Luzi-Kihupi A, Zakayo AJ. 2001. Performance of early maturing mutants derived from Supa rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) cultivar. Tanzania J. Agric. Sci. 4:37-44.